

A STUDY ON E-PAYMENT TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO RAMANATHAPURAM DISTRICT

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

E-payment has revolutionized the way we shop online, making transactions quick, convenient, and secure. It has greatly impacted online shopping behaviour in several ways. E-payment has made the entire online shopping experience more seamless. With traditional payment methods like cash-on-delivery or bank transfers, customers had to go through a lengthy and often cumbersome process to complete their purchase.

E-payment has also led to changes in consumer behaviour when it comes to price comparison and shopping habits. With the ease of online payments, customers are now more inclined to compare prices across different online retailers, searching for the best deals. This has created a more competitive environment for online sellers as customers have access to a wider range of options and can easily switch between sellers to find the best price. Additionally, e-payment has made it easier for customers to shop from international online retailers, broadening their choices and allowing them to order products from around the world.

E-payment has also influenced impulse buying behaviour. With the ease of making payments online, customers can quickly purchase items on a whim without much thought or consideration. This has led to an increase in impulse purchases, as customers are more likely to make spontaneous buying decisions when the purchasing process is simplified.

E-payment has also impacted customer loyalty and repeat purchases. With the convenience of stored payment information, customers can easily make repeat purchases from their favourite online retailers without having to re-enter their payment details each time. This has led to increased customer loyalty and repeat business, as customers find it more convenient to shop from retailers that offer e-payment options. In this study focused or examine impact of e-payment on online shopping behaviour with special reference to Ramanathapuram district.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To study and analyse the impact of e-payment on online shopping behaviour and identify the factors influencing consumers' adoption of e-payment methods in online shopping, as well as the challenges and benefits associated

with using e-payment for online purchases. The increased availability and convenience of e-payment methods has transformed the way people shop online. This project aims to examine the impact of e-payment on consumers' online shopping behaviour and understand the factors that influence their adoption of e-payment methods. By doing so, this study will contribute to our understanding of the challenges and benefits associated with using e-payment for online purchases.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyse the influence of e-payment on consumers' willingness to make online purchases.
2. To examine the role of e-payment in enhancing the convenience and speed of online shopping.
3. To offer the findings and suggestions towards e-payment on online shopping behaviour.

1.4 PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study covers a period of six months from November 2023 to April 2024 data related to six months have been collected from the E-Payment on Online Shopping in Ramanathapuram District.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data has been collected by using well designed questionnaire. The sample was a non-probability sampling consists of 100 respondents who have purchasing online through e-payment method in Ramanathapuram district. The data was collected through questionnaire and it was structured with both open ended and closed ended questions to get better insight of the respondents. The questionnaire was revised with the help of impact on e-payment towards online shopping behaviour in Ramanathapuram district and to strengthen its validity, the questionnaire was circulated among the respondents who have purchasing online through e-payment method. Based on the feedback received from them it was modified. The secondary data has been collected from the books, newspaper, related journals, magazines and internet.

1.5.1 Sampling design

Non-probability sampling is the sampling procedure which does not afford any basis for the probability that each item in the population has of being included in the sample. Non-probability sampling is also known by different names such as deliberate sampling, purposive, sampling and judgment sampling.

The convenient sampling method was adopted to select 100 sample respondents. Care was taken to give due representation to include the consumer (i.e) from business, professional, salaried group and so on.

1.6 TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The general plan of analysis ranges for simple percentage tables to advanced statistical tools. For the purpose of testing various Percentage Analysis, Weighted Arithmetic Mean, Anova, Chi-square Test and Correlation.

1.7 AREA OF STUDY

The present study concentrated on finding out the E-payment on online shopping consumers behaviour in Ramanathapuram district. The area of the study is the Ramanathapuram district.

1.8 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Time and cost will be factors which have limited the size of sample as 100.
- This study will be restricted to Ramanathapuram District only.
- Findings and conclusions of the study are applicable to those zones only. Therefore, the finding out of the study cannot be generalised at all places.
- Conclusions were made on the opinion given by the respondents.

4.2.19 THE BENEFITS OF USING E-PAYMENT METHODS FOR ONLINE SHOPPING

The following table shows the benefits of using e-payment methods for online shopping.

TABLE 4.19

THE BENEFITS OF USING E-PAYMENT METHODS FOR ONLINE SHOPPING

S. No.	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Faster checkout process	25	25
2	Availability of multiple payment options	28	28
3	Secure transactions	18	18
4	Cash back and rewards	29	29
	Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

It is seen from the table that 29% of the respondents are realised that benefits of using e-payment methods for cash back and rewards, 28% of the respondents are felt that benefits of using e-payment methods for availability of multiple payment options, 25% of the respondents are mentioned that benefits of using e-payment methods for faster checkout process, and remaining 18% of the respondents are felt that secure transactions.

From this, it is observed that the majority of the respondents are realised that benefits of using e-payment methods for cash back and rewards.

1.9 FINDINGS

- 75% of the respondents are female in the present study.
- As far as age is concerned the majority of the respondents are in the age group of 21 to 40 years.
- Hence, it is clear that 43% of the respondents are Bachelor degree.
- 72% of the respondents are unmarried.
- 63% of the respondents are Student.
- From the study it is clear that 38% of the respondents are having family income less than Rs. 20,000.
- Hence, it is clear that 59% of the respondents are living in urban area.
- From this analysis, it is observed that 92% of the respondents are purchasing through online shopping.
- Hence, it is clear that 52% of the respondents are purchased the clothing and footwear.
- Majority of the respondents are preferred the Cash on delivery.
- From the analysis, it is clear that 45% of the respondents are not sure about e-payment methods are more secured than traditional payment methods.
- From this analysis, it is observed that 38% of the respondents are preferred technical issues.
- 47% of the respondents are preferred the only for small purchases.
- Majority of the Respondents are preferred the e-wallets.
- From the analysis, it is clear that 45% of the respondents are chosen the faster transaction processing.
- The respondents level of satisfaction towards the E-payment options may lead to overspending due to disconnect between physical money and virtual transactions is moderate.
- It is clear that the respondents level of satisfaction towards the E-payment options enhances consumer trust in online shopping platforms is moderate.
- The respondents level of satisfaction towards the E-payment options encourages consumers to shop more frequently online is moderate.
- The percentage of satisfaction of the respondents towards E-payment options allow for easy tracking of online shopping expenses is 69.11%.
- The respondents level of satisfaction towards the E-payment options may lead to a decrease in cash transactions, impacting traditional brick-and-mortar stores is moderate.
- The correlation is applied to find out the relationship between age and the number of hours spends with online shopping by the customers.
- The co-efficient of correlation (r) is -0.85. Hence it is concluded that there is a negative correlation between age and number of hours spends with online shopping by the customers.
- The Chi-square test was adopted to find out the association between age and customers decision factor influenced to use e-payment while shopping online. The hypothesis framed for chi-square test is
 - There is no significant difference between age and customers decision factor influenced to use e-payment while shopping online.
- The calculated value of chi-square test is 11.5128 less than the table value of 21.026 hence, the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no relationship between age of respondents and customers decision factor influenced to use e-payment while shopping online.

- Two-way Anova was applied to find out the relationship between educational level and reason for preferred mode of payment when shopping online. The hypothesis framed are
 - Reason for preferred mode of payment does not differ among the customers when shopping online.
 - Reason for preferred E-payment does not differ with respect to educational level of the customers.
- The calculated value of 7.24 is more than the table value of 3.49. The hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that the reason for preferred mode of payment differ among the customers when shopping online.
- The calculated value of 1.32 is less than of the table value of 3.26. The hypothesis holds true. Hence, the reason for preferred the e-payment does not differ with respect to educational level of the customers.

1.10 SUGGESTIONS

- ✓ Consumers believe that e-payment has greatly enhanced the convenience of online shopping. It makes the checkout process much quicker and easier, encouraging consumers to make more online purchases.
- ✓ E-payment has definitely increased their online shopping frequency. The ability to securely store their payment information and quickly make transactions has made consumers more inclined to shop online.
- ✓ As a frequent online shopper, consumers can say that e-payment has made a significant impact on their purchasing behaviour. It's fast, secure, and eliminates the hassle of entering their payment information every time consumers shop online.
- ✓ The delivery person makes sure the order, it received by the customer or not.
- ✓ E-payment methods are comfortable but still it lacks safety and security.
- ✓ Being user friendly apps will be more helpful for the customers.
- ✓ E-payment has made consumers more comfortable shopping online, especially with the added layers of security and convenience it offers. Consumers find themselves making larger purchases knowing that their payment information is protected

1.11 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the impact of e-payment towards online shopping behaviour in Ramanathapuram is highly significant. The convenience, security, and ease of use of e-payment methods have contributed to the increasing popularity of online shopping in the region. With more and more consumers opting for online shopping, businesses are also adapting to this trend by expanding their online presence and offering various e-payment options. Overall, e-payment has transformed the shopping experience in Ramanathapuram, making it more convenient and accessible for consumers.

Additionally, the shift towards e-payment has also opened up new opportunities for businesses to reach a wider audience and drive sales. It has also provided consumers with a safer and more convenient way to make transactions, which has further fuelled the growth of online shopping in the region. Overall, the impact of e-

payment on online shopping behaviour in Ramanathapuram is positive and is likely to continue to shape the way consumers shop in the future.

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